

Efficient Crop Mapping via Temporal Transfer under Data Constraints

Miloš Pandžić^{1,*}, Dejan Pavlović¹, Sanja Brdar¹, Jelena Pandžić², Oskar Marko¹, Milan Kilibarda³

¹ BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, milos.pandzic@biosense.rs, dejan.pavlovic@biosense.rs, sanja.brada@biosense.rs, oskar.marko@biosense.rs

² Academy of Technical and Art Applied Studies Belgrade, School of Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Belgrade, Serbia, jelenapandzic@viggs.rs

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia, kili@grf.bg.ac.rs

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20395822

Abstract: Large-scale applied crop mapping from satellite imagery faces persistent challenges related to the cost and availability of labelled training data, particularly early in the growing season when timely maps are most needed. While transfer learning has shown promise for reusing models trained on historical data, its practical effectiveness under real-world operational constraints remains underexplored. This study evaluates temporal transfer learning for crop classification using Sentinel-1 SAR time series, focusing on three operationally relevant scenarios: spatially clustered ground sampling, early-season mapping with incomplete time series, and reduced satellite availability following the Sentinel-1B malfunction. Building on previous work that compared multiple architectures, we focus exclusively on the best-performing CNN-1D model and investigate optimal proportions of target-domain data for retraining. Validation experiments identified that performance saturates at approximately 50% of available samples, with diminishing returns beyond this point. Three efficient retraining proportions (4%, 7%, 19%) were selected and evaluated on an independent test dataset, achieving F1 scores of 83%, 84%, and 86%, respectively—approximately 7% higher than training from scratch with improved stability. Spatially clustered sampling within 20-30 km buffers maintained strong performance (74-83% F1) while substantially reducing field survey costs. Early-season mapping with partial time series consistently outperformed alternatives, and transfer learning proved most resilient under reduced satellite availability (79% F1 versus 76% from scratch). These findings demonstrate that transfer learning provides a robust, practical strategy for operational crop mapping under logistical, temporal, and technical constraints encountered in real-world agricultural monitoring.

Keywords: temporal transfer learning; crop mapping; Sentinel-1; convolutional neural network.

1 Introduction

Accurate crop type mapping from remote sensing is essential for food security monitoring, yield forecasting, and agricultural policy (Joshi et al. 2023). Dense Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time series are now primary data sources, with machine learning models exploiting temporal dynamics for large-scale mapping (Rußwurm and Körner 2020, Blickensdörfer et al. 2022). However, operational deployment remains constrained by the need for large labelled datasets, which are costly and often unavailable

early in the season when maps are most needed (Lin et al. 2022).

Transfer learning addresses this limitation by adapting models trained on historical (source) seasons to a new (target) season with limited supervision. It leverages knowledge from one domain to improve learning in another while reducing labelling requirements (Zhuang et al. 2020). Previous studies demonstrated that transferring learned temporal representations improves crop classification under scarce target data, particularly for deep models (Rusňák et al. 2023, Pandžić et al. 2024a). Nevertheless, benefits depend on target data availability and source-target similarity and may diminish once sufficient labels are collected.

In Pandžić et al. (2024a), we compared transfer strategies against season-specific training using Sentinel-1 time series and showed that transfer learning was most advantageous under limited target data, while models trained from scratch closed the gap as data increased. The present study extends this work (preliminary results in Pandžić et al. 2024b) by focusing on the best-performing CNN-1D model and three practical scenarios: spatially clustered sampling, early-season mapping with partial time series, and reduced satellite availability (Sentinel-1B malfunction). The objective is to assess whether transfer learning retains operational value under realistic logistical, temporal, and technical constraints.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted in Vojvodina ($\approx 21,500 \text{ km}^2$) in northern Serbia, a flat and intensively cultivated region within the Pannonian Basin characterized by moderate continental climate and inter-annual variability. Fragmented agricultural parcels motivate pixel-level classification. Ground reference data were collected annually from 2017–2021 through field campaigns, with crop types recorded via GPS and linked to parcel boundaries derived from optical imagery. Nine major crops were considered: corn, wheat, soybean, sunflower, sugar beet, oilseed rape, barley, clover, and orchard. Pixels were randomly sampled to form training, validation, and test sets, ensuring no data leakage. Seasons 2017–2020 served as the source domain and 2021 as the target domain. Sentinel-1 SAR time series (Interferometric Wide mode, Level-1 GRD) provided cloud-independent observations. Standard preprocessing: orbit correction, radiometric calibration, speckle filtering, terrain flattening, and terrain

correction, produced spatially aligned backscatter time series. Further details are given in Pandžić et al. (2024a).

We adopt the CNN-1D model identified as optimal in Pandžić et al. (2024a) and evaluate temporal transfer from historical seasons (2017–2020) to 2021. The network was first pre-trained on the source domain and subsequently fine-tuned using varying proportions of target-season samples. Performance was assessed using F1 score to account for class imbalance.

To identify operationally relevant retraining proportions, we analyzed performance curves across increasing target-sample ratios and applied knee-point analysis to determine points of diminishing returns. These proportions were then used consistently across experiments. All decisions were based exclusively on validation performance (test set reserved for final confirmation), using the best historical cross-validation fold as the pre-trained model (three seasons as source, one as pseudo-target), with retraining ratios (1–20%) evaluated via 5-fold cross-validation alongside training-from-scratch and pure-transfer baselines.

Then three practical scenarios were evaluated. First, spatially clustered sampling was simulated by selecting target samples within buffers of increasing radius around a single departure point, mimicking realistic field-survey constraints. Second, early-season mapping was assessed by truncating time series at successive points (June–August) to evaluate partial-season performance. Third, reduced satellite availability was simulated by excluding Sentinel-1B acquisitions, effectively halving temporal density.

3 Results

Model performance depended strongly on the proportion of target-season samples used for fine-tuning. Pure transfer achieved an F1 score of 81%, demonstrating substantial cross-season knowledge transfer. Introducing target samples progressively improved performance, reaching 90% when nearly all labels were used. Notably, accuracy saturated early, with approximately half the samples yielding 88% F1. Training from scratch performed

Figure 1. Results of various CNN approaches on the corresponding validation dataset. Pure transfer of pre-trained model is given under the no training label, transfer learning approach is denoted by TL, and training model from scratch is denoted by FS. Decision on optimal points for testing the selected model on the test dataset are given as vertical dashed lines.

markedly worse under limited data. Knee-point analysis identified three operationally relevant retraining proportions: 4%, 7%, and 19% (Figure 1).

On the independent 2021 test set (Figure 2), transfer learning achieved F1 scores of 83%, 84%, and 86% for 4%, 7%, and 19% retraining proportions, respectively. Compared to training from scratch, transfer learning improved performance by approximately 7% on average and reduced variability (1.4% vs. 2.7%).

Figure 2. The performance of the transfer learning approach (TL), pure transfer of the pre-trained model (no training), and the model trained from scratch (FS) on the test dataset when geographically distributed samples are used for re-training.

Under spatially clustered sampling (buffers of ~20, 25, and 30 km), transfer learning achieved F1 scores of 74%, 79%, and 83%, consistently outperforming training from scratch by about 5%, though with moderate decreases compared to spatially distributed sampling (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3. Ground truth data for the 2021 test season (red dot is the province capital Novi Sad, the departure point for the ground survey, the blue circle denotes a ~20 km radius, the magenta circle denotes a ~25 km radius, the cyan circle denotes a ~30 km radius, labelled polygons during field campaign are shown in purple and green).

For early-season mapping (19% samples, 30 km buffer), transfer learning achieved 72% F1 by late June, improving to 74% in July and 78% in August (Table 1).

Under reduced satellite availability (Sentinel-1A only), transfer learning achieved 79% F1, compared to 76% for training from scratch and 48% for pure transfer (Table 2).

Figure 4. The performance of the transfer learning approach (TL), pure transfer of the pre-trained model (no training), and the model trained from scratch (FS) on the test dataset when geographically grouped samples are used for re/training.

Table 1. F1 score on test set for early-season and end-of-season crop mapping.

Month	CNN no training	CNN TL	CNN FS
June	0.41	0.72	0.71
July	0.59	0.74	0.74
August	0.70	0.78	0.77
September	0.78	0.83	0.78

Table 2. End-of-season crop mapping results on test set using the single satellite and using both satellites.

Satellite	CNN no training	CNN TL	CNN FS
Sentinel-1A	0.48	0.79	0.76
Sentinel-1A and -1B	0.78	0.83	0.78

4 Discussion

Results confirm that transfer learning provides clear advantages under limited target-season data, both in accuracy and robustness. Performance gains were most pronounced at low retraining proportions, while differences diminished as more labels became available.

Spatially clustered sampling led to moderate performance reductions, likely due to reduced representativeness (Orynbaikyzy et al. 2022), yet transfer learning maintained a consistent advantage. This indicates a favourable trade-off between labelling effort and classification accuracy in operational surveys.

Consistent with observations in Račić et al. (2024), transfer learning enabled reliable crop mapping before full temporal information was available (early-season scenarios). In addition, it outperformed pure transfer and remained competitive with training from scratch. This is particularly relevant for timely agricultural decision-making.

Finally, under reduced temporal sampling caused by Sentinel-1B malfunction, transfer learning proved more resilient than alternative strategies. Despite a slight overall accuracy decrease, it remained the most robust approach, highlighting its practical value under logistical and technical constraints.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that temporal transfer learning provides a robust and practically viable strategy for operational crop mapping under realistic constraints. By reusing knowledge from historical satellite time series, transfer learning enables reliable classification with substantially reduced ground truth requirements while exhibiting improved stability compared to training from scratch. Performance gains saturate relatively early as additional target data are introduced, with approximately 50% of available samples yielding near-maximum accuracy. This finding emphasizes the importance of identifying efficient operating points that balance labelling effort and expected performance.

Three practical scenarios confirm that transfer learning remains effective even when data availability is constrained by logistics or sensor limitations. Spatially clustered sampling, which concentrates field surveys in localized areas, achieved strong performance with moderate accuracy trade-offs relative to distributed sampling. Early-season mapping demonstrated that transfer learning consistently outperforms alternatives when time series are incomplete, addressing the operational need for timely crop information. Finally, reduced satellite availability experiments showed that transfer learning maintains resilience when observation frequency is compromised, an increasingly relevant consideration for aging satellite constellations.

Overall, these findings support transfer learning as a key methodological component for timely, scalable, and cost-efficient crop mapping systems, bridging the gap between research-oriented model development and real-world agricultural monitoring applications. Future work should explore transfer learning across different geographic regions and investigate its performance under additional operational constraints, such as variable weather conditions and emerging sensor technologies.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-33/2026-03/200358).

6 References

- Blickensdörfer, L., Schwieder, M., Pflugmacher, D., Nendel, C., Erasmí, S., Hostert, P., 2022. Mapping of crop types and crop sequences with combined time series of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data for Germany. *Remote sensing of environment*, 269, p.112831.
- Joshi, A., Pradhan, B., Gite, S., Chakraborty, S., 2023. Remote-sensing data and deep-learning techniques in crop mapping and yield prediction: A systematic review. *Remote Sensing*, 15(8), p.2014.
- Lin, C., Zhong, L., Song, X.P., Dong, J., Lobell, D.B., Jin, Z., 2022. Early-and in-season crop type mapping without current-year ground truth: Generating labels from historical information via a topology-based approach. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 274, p.112994.
- Orynbaikyzy, A., Gessner, U., Conrad, C., 2022. Spatial transferability of random forest models for crop type

- classification using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2. *Remote Sensing*, 14(6), p.1493.
- Pandžić, M., Pavlović, D., Matavulj, P., Brdar, S., Marko, O., Crnojević, V., Kilibarda, M., 2024a. Interseasonal transfer learning for crop mapping using Sentinel-1 data. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 128, p.103718.
- Pandžić, M., Pavlović, D., Brdar, S., Kilibarda, M., Marko, O., 2024b. Cracking Ground Truth Barriers: Harnessing the Power of Transfer Learning for Crop Mapping. *European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2024 (EGU24)*, p.3127.
- Račić, M., Oštir, K., Zupanc, A., Čehovin Zajc, L., 2024. Multi-year time series transfer learning: Application of early crop classification. *Remote Sensing*, 16(2), p.270.
- Rušňák, T., Kasanický, T., Malík, P., Mojžiš, J., Zelenka, J., Sviček, M., Abrahám, D., Halabuk, A., 2023. Crop mapping without labels: Investigating temporal and spatial transferability of crop classification models using a 5-year sentinel-2 series and machine learning. *Remote Sensing*, 15(13), p.3414.
- Rußwurm, M., Körner, M., 2020. Self-attention for raw optical satellite time series classification. *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing*, 169, pp.421-435.
- Zhuang, F., Qi, Z., Duan, K., Xi, D., Zhu, Y., Zhu, H., Xiong, H., He, Q., 2020. A comprehensive survey on transfer learning. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 109(1), pp.43-76.